

The Impact of the Syrian Reality on Strategic Plans in the Eastern Mediterranean

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Abstract

This article investigates how the Syrian civil war affects regional and global dynamics, as well as strategic aims in the Eastern Mediterranean. Historically a source of conflict between major countries, the Middle East and Eastern Mediterranean have become unstable areas with rising tensions, proxy conflicts, and internal instability. This instability stems from Syria's civil war. The article investigates the Syrian civil war's origins, development, and multilayered structure, as well as the role of regional and global players and proxy battles. It also evaluates potential future scenarios for Syria (the development of a new state and constitution, a federative structure, and a split Syria) and the risks associated with each. Other significant concerns raised in the piece include oil geopolitics in the Eastern Mediterranean, the Cyprus crisis, and Israeli involvement. The essay also discusses the harm caused by exterior actions in the area using the rhetoric of "bringing democracy" and the humanitarian element of the migrant crisis. Finally, it will be highlighted that the future of Syria and the Eastern Mediterranean is uncertain, and that multifaceted efforts and international collaboration are required to find a long-term solution.

Keywords: *Syria, Eastern Mediterranean, Strategic Plans, Proxy Wars, Energy Geopolitics, Cyprus Problem, Israel, External Interventions, Migration Crisis and International Cooperation*

1. Introduction

Because of its strategic significance, huge oil resources, and geopolitical position, the Middle East and Eastern Mediterranean have long been the focus of major power struggles and influence activities. This attitude remains unchanged today, as growing tensions, proxy wars, increased participation of non-state players, internal conflicts, the refugee crisis, and sociopolitical fault lines have destabilized the area. This study will look at trends in the Middle East and Eastern Mediterranean, particularly the civil war in Syria, and how it affects regional and global dynamics from a political science standpoint. The future structure of Syria, the roles of regional and global players, and regional power conflicts will be investigated in light of economic, political, social, and religious considerations.

2. Aim

The continuing civil conflict in Syria has had disastrous repercussions, displacing millions of people and causing a massive migratory problem in the area (Kataibeh & AL-Labady, 2014). This crisis has imposed tremendous costs not just on Syria's neighbouring nations, but also on Europe as a whole. The human security approach highlights the need of prioritizing the humanitarian aspects of the issue while also protecting the rights and well-being of those impacted. (Silverburg and Alshdaifat, 2017). (Lynch, 2017). This essay contends that the Syrian civil war and developments in the Eastern Mediterranean form a complex and varied set of issues that jeopardize regional and global security.

3. Methodology

More than a decade of violence has almost ripped Syria apart. Syria's future direction is vital for regional stability. Three main concerns stand out in this respect, as do the hazards they pose:

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- • Creating a New State and Constitution: This scenario aims to establish a new state structure and constitution that is recognized by all sides in the Syrian conflict and society. It is vital to conduct an inclusive political process, implement transitional justice measures, and establish democratic institutions. However, tremendous animosity between the parties, ideological divisions, and the presence of other factors make this scenario implausible.
- • Syria would be split into areas administered by different ethnic and religious groupings, creating a federative structure. This scenario would provide autonomy to Kurdish-controlled territory. However, little information is available on how a federative structure would operate, how the central government would transfer power to the federative regions, or if other regional players would accept this arrangement.
- • The fall of the central authority has left Syria divided, with multiple entities dominating different sections of the nation. This is also known as "Somalization" and is the region's most lethal situation. It has the potential to bolster terrorist and organized criminal networks, intensify the humanitarian crisis, and heighten regional instability.

4. Literature Review

The Syrian civil war has been a complex and varied conflict, with an extensive scholarly literature exploring many facets of the crisis, such as conflict dynamics, regional and global participation, energy geopolitics, proxy warfare, and humanitarian consequences. (Holland, 2020). From a theoretical standpoint, the acts of nations participating in the war may be studied through the prism of realism and neo-realist viewpoints, which prioritize security and national interests. (Awaad, 2020). Scholars such as Waltz and Mearsheimer have suggested that such a worldview might cause conflict in international politics. (Liang 2021) Alternatively, shortcomings in state and nation development, as described by Fukuyama and Paris, may contribute to Syria's instability and bloodshed. Furthermore, Jervis' security problem may assist to explain the Syrian conflict's weapons race and proxy warfare. (Holland, 2020). Extensive

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research has been conducted on the role of regional and global powers, as well as the dynamics of proxy warfare. Energy geopolitics in the Eastern Mediterranean, where natural resources have been found, has played a significant role in regional conflicts. Yergin's research on the issue of energy security provides useful insights into these processes. From a critical standpoint, postcolonial and structural perspectives such as those of Said and Fanon question the West's domination and the implications of its interventions under the guise of "bringing democracy." According to realism and neo-realist perspectives, states participating in the Syrian war are prioritizing their own security and national interests, which has resulted in rising tensions and bloodshed. (Awaad, 2020). This viewpoint is crucial for examining the motives and tactics of the conflict's primary participants. In contrast, as Fukuyama and Paris have underlined, failings in state and nation development may lead to the instability and bloodshed in Syria. Jervis's security dilemma offers a framework for analyzing the Syrian conflict's arms race and proxy war, in which governments' security measures are regarded as threats by other states, resulting in further escalation. (Holland, 2020). (Awaad, 2020).

Scholars like as Mumford and Byman have conducted substantial research into the role of regional and global powers, as well as the dynamics of proxy warfare. The energy geopolitics of the Eastern Mediterranean, where natural resources have been found, has also played a role in regional tensions, as Yergin points out in his work on the significance of energy security. From a critical standpoint, postcolonial and structural perspectives such as those of Said and Fanon attack the West's domination and the implications of its interventions under the guise of "bringing democracy". (Bichler, Nitzan, 2014) (Awaad, 2020). (Hu et al.,2022) Blondeel et al. (2021) To summarize, the Syrian civil war has been a complicated and varied struggle that has resulted in an extensive scholarly literature. The theoretical views and geopolitical issues discussed in this essay give a thorough grasp of the numerous forces and dynamics at work in this lengthy and catastrophic crisis. (Bichler, Nitzan, 2014) (Bichler, Nitzan, 2014) (Awaad, 2020). Blondeel et al. (2021)

The country's divided political and social structures have contributed significantly to the current turmoil. Jervis' idea of the "security dilemma" may also assist explain conflict dynamics, in which governments' security measures are regarded as threats by others, leading to an arms

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race and proxy war. (Awaad, 2020). (Holland, 2020). Mumford and Byman's research on proxy conflicts is especially essential for understanding the Syrian civil war, which has become a perfect example of a conflict in which regional and global powers assist different parties. (Gaber, 2020). (Awaad, 2020).

Furthermore, as Yergin argues, the significance of energy resources and the hunt for energy security have been significant contributors to regional tensions in the Eastern Mediterranean, where the discovery of natural gas has added a new layer of complexity to the war. (Awaad, 2020). From a postcolonial and structural standpoint, the West's activities and interventions under the slogan of "bringing democracy" may be critically scrutinized. While Said and Fanon's books provide useful insights into power dynamics and the "othering" of non-Western civilizations, Wendt's focus on identities and norms in international relations gives light on the implications of such interventions. The criticisms of the West's control over the "other" by Said and Fanon, as well as Wendt's focus on the significance of identities and norms in international relations, offer useful frameworks for assessing the repercussions of such interventions in the context of the Syrian civil war. The current literature on the Syrian civil war, as shown by the materials offered, provides a varied picture of the conflict, stressing the numerous theoretical perspectives and geopolitical elements that impact its dynamics and consequences. (Holland, 2020). (Gaber, 2020). (Awaad, 2020).

4.1. Syrian Civil War: Its Beginning, Development and Multi-Layered Structure

The peaceful protests that started in 2011 in Syria, spurred by the Arab Spring and a desire for democratic reform, swiftly devolved into a terrible civil war as a consequence of the regime's violent crackdown. During this time, it was evident that Syria was no longer only a domestic conflict, but was quickly becoming the focal point of proxy warfare between regional and global powers. Syria has been de facto fragmented, with sections controlled by diverse ethnic, religious, and ideological factions, highlighting the inadequacies of state-building and nation-building processes. The rise of extreme terrorist organizations like ISIS, as well as the danger they represent to regional security, may be seen via the security dilemma lens. The authoritarian government's

severe tactics have highlighted deep-rooted social, political, and religious divisions in Syrian society, resulting in identity politics and sectarian conflict.

4.2 The Role of Regional and Global Actors: The Theatre of Proxy Wars

Regional and global countries interfered in the Syrian civil war to further their own goals, significantly altering the conflict's trajectory and the regional balance of power. Countries like the United States, Russia, Iran, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and Qatar fought proxy wars by sponsoring different groups. The presence and activity of these groups in Syria have exacerbated the civil strife.

4.3 Scenarios for Syria's Future: Uncertainty and Risks

Over a decade of fighting in Syria has resulted in upheaval, significantly affecting the region's stability. Three main options have arisen about Syria's future, each accompanied by distinct dangers and difficulties.

1. The first scenario anticipates the establishment of a new state framework and constitution, developed via an inclusive political process that engages all warring parties and all parts of Syrian society. This necessitates the implementation of transitional justice measures and the establishment of democratic institutions. Nevertheless, considerable distrust among the parties, ideological conflicts, and the involvement of other entities make this scenario improbable.
2. The second possibility is partitioning Syria into autonomous territories administered by various ethnic and religious factions, culminating in a federal structure. This may possibly include autonomy for territories governed by Kurds. However, the actual execution of a federative structure, the allocation of competences between the central government and the federated regions, and the endorsement of this system by other regional entities remain ambiguous (Liang, 2021).

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3. The third and most concerning possibility is the fragmentation of Syria, with disparate groups governing various regions of the nation as a result of the central government's collapse. The "Somalization" of Syria may intensify the humanitarian catastrophe, bolster terrorist and organized criminal networks, and further destabilize the area. (Dobbins et al., 2015) Walther and Pedersen (2020) Holland, 2020

5. Argument

The crisis in Syria is a complicated and diverse situation that has evolved through numerous different periods. The crisis, initially motivated by demands for human rights and democratic change, rapidly transformed into a conflict centered on the deployment of chemical weapons and the emergence of Islamist extremism, ultimately evolving into a proxy war involving regional and global forces. Holland, 2020 The spillover effects of the civil conflict, particularly the refugee crisis, have resulted in significant repercussions, taxing the resources and unity of neighboring nations and the wider international community. Liang (2021)

Given the uncertain future of Syria, it is imperative that the international community endeavors to establish a comprehensive and permanent resolution that tackles the underlying causes of the conflict, fosters reconciliation, and guarantees the stability and welfare of the Syrian people. Walther and Pedersen (2020) Dobbins et al. (2015) Liang (2021) (Holland, 2020)

5.1 Increasing Competition in the Eastern Mediterranean: Energy Geopolitics, Cyprus and the Balance of Power

The identification of substantial hydrocarbon deposits in the Eastern Mediterranean has incited a multifaceted power conflict among the coastal nations, each competing for dominion and extraction rights over these precious energy resources. Energy geopolitics has emerged as a crucial framework for comprehending shifting regional dynamics, as nations like Israel, Cyprus, Greece,

Egypt, and Turkey compete for influence and establish new alliances to safeguard their energy interests. Blondeel et al. (2021)

Cyprus's strategic position, coupled with its unsettled political status since 1974, has rendered it a significant participant in this energy conflict. The island's strategic position has heightened its significance, as military installations, the persistent Syrian civil conflict, and the concept of a two-state solution exacerbate regional instability. The likelihood of more war in the Eastern Mediterranean is heightened by inherent deficiencies in the international and regional frameworks that seek to reconcile conflicting standards and political epochs. Richmond, 1999 Recent regional tensions have prompted a succession of diplomatic initiatives; yet, in reaction to perceived security challenges, Greece has implemented a strategy of abyss to heighten world awareness of the dangers of a future confrontation with Turkey. Richmond, 1999 Conversely, Turkey has endeavored to bolster its assertion in the Eastern Mediterranean by negotiating a maritime jurisdiction delimitation agreement with the Libyan Government of National Accord, therefore further complicating regional power relations.

The strategic positioning of the Eastern Mediterranean, which includes the Mediterranean, Aegean, and Black Seas, has historically been a significant determinant of the region's geopolitical relevance. The region's energy resources, including a substantial share of the world's confirmed oil and natural gas reserves, have heightened the hazards for the coastal nations concerned. (Aburas & Demirbaş, 2015)

The involvement of foreign countries like the United States and Russia exacerbates the energy geopolitics in the Eastern Mediterranean.

5.2 The Israeli Factor

Israel is expanding its military and political hegemony in the Eastern Mediterranean. The discoveries of natural gas, strong links with the United States, and military capabilities enhance the regional balance of power. The impact of the new Syrian organization on Israel's regional strategy and the balance of power in the Eastern Mediterranean remains ambiguous.

5.3 The "Bringing Democracy" Discourse and the Bitter Legacy of Foreign Interventions

The military interventions executed by the West under the banner of "promoting democracy in the Middle East" have resulted in regional upheaval and instability. The events of Iraq and Libya illustrate the catastrophic outcomes of military interventions. Postcolonial theory posits that these interventions perpetuate the West's attempts to assert domination over the "other" by universalizing its norms and standards. Structuralists argue that enforcing a "democracy model" that disregards local dynamics, historical context, and cultural variety is destined for failure.

5.4 Migration Crisis: Enduring Humanitarian Tragedy and Responsibility

The Syrian civil conflict and regional instability have resulted in the displacement of millions and precipitated a significant migratory crisis. This has emerged as a significant issue not just for the nations in the area but also for Europe. The human security approach underscores the significance of the human aspect of this catastrophe and the need to safeguard persons. The international community must assume more responsibility to address this issue, provide humanitarian aid, and formulate more inclusive policies for refugees.

The Syrian war has markedly exacerbated pre-existing ethnic and sectarian tensions, resulting in the emergence of extremist factions and the proliferation of other issues, including the refugee crisis. Liang, 2021. As of 2019, there were over 6.6 million refugees in Syria, with approximately 60% classified as insufficient. Liang (2021) A significant number of these people have sought asylum in neighboring nations, particularly Turkey, which has emerged as the country hosting the highest number of refugees globally. (Allahi et al., 2020) (Bahcekapili & Cetin, 2015)

The relocation of Syrians has prompted significant inquiries about the ramifications of international law and the rights and status of refugees. Countries accommodating the bulk of Syrian refugees, including Jordan, Lebanon, Egypt, and Turkey, have had challenges in addressing the support and protection requirements of both the recent inflow of refugees and the established refugee community. Silverburg and Alshdaifat (2017) Humanitarian groups have historically

offered in-kind aid to these populations; however, there is a growing acknowledgment of the need for more inclusive and dignified strategies, such as cash-based interventions, to address the long-term needs of refugees. (Allahi et al., 2020) (Kataibeh & Al-Labady, 2014)

The international community must implement a more holistic and accountable strategy to tackle the Syrian refugee crisis, which includes augmenting humanitarian aid, formulating more inclusive and rights-oriented policies for refugees, and striving to resolve the fundamental conflict in Syria. Countries hosting the bulk of the refugee surge, including Jordan, Lebanon, Egypt, and Turkey, are facing challenges in addressing the relief and protection requirements of both the recent Syrian refugees and the pre-existing refugee population inside their borders. Silverburg and Alshdaifat (2017) Consequently, the international community has the obligation to provide more extensive humanitarian aid and formulate more inclusive policies for refugees. Altun, 2021 (Allahi et al., 2020) (Kataibeh and Al-Labady, 2014).

The humanitarian perspective on the Syrian refugee crisis underscores the need for the international community to adopt a more proactive position in addressing the situation and offering support to those impacted. This includes augmenting financial support for humanitarian aid, broadening resettlement initiatives, and advocating for policies that uphold the rights and dignity of refugees (Kataibeh & AL-Labady, 2014).

5.5 Discussion Question

"Can the intricate and multifaceted issues arising from the Syrian civil war and developments in the Eastern Mediterranean be addressed through international collaboration and multilateral diplomacy, or is the region destined for prolonged instability and conflict?"

5.6 Claim

The Syrian civil conflict and the developments in the Eastern Mediterranean represent a complex and multidimensional array of issues that jeopardize both regional and global security. These issues can alone be resolved by international collaboration, multilateral diplomacy, inclusive political frameworks, fair resource distribution, and an emphasis on local dynamics. Otherwise, the area will be ensnared in a protracted cycle of instability and bloodshed. It is evident that resolving the situation in Syria and the broader region would be challenging. It would be ludicrous to anticipate cultivating a bed of flowers among years of persistent strife, intensifying issues, and a convoluted network of relationships. Enduring, diligent, and thorough efforts are necessary to attain enduring peace and stability in this challenging area. Nonetheless, our foremost duty is to maintain optimism and to endeavor towards this goal.

5.7 Criticism

A significant limitation of the research is its emphasis on a dynamic and constantly evolving environment. Research and forecasts of daily fluctuations may rapidly become obsolete. The substantial number of individuals and the intricate interests of the area complicate comprehensive research. Thus, this work ought to be regarded as a preliminary overview and a foundation for further investigation.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

A multitude of elements will converge to shape the future of Syria, the Middle East, and the Eastern Mediterranean. The right of regional states to self-determination must be upheld within the framework of the concept of self-determination. Nonetheless, among foreign involvement, proxy warfare, and profound social, political, and religious divisions, constructing a genuine and liberated future will pose a significant challenge. A sustainable solution may be attained not alone by military intervention, but also via diplomatic initiatives, social consensus, inclusive democratic procedures, economic development, and fair resource distribution. The Syrian crisis necessitates

increased involvement from the international community in humanitarian assistance delivery, refugee management, political resolution support, and the prevention of impunity for war crimes.

7. References

- Aburas, H. M., & Demirbaş, A. (2015). Caspian Sea Basin, Middle East Petroleum Resources and Their Importance for Turkey. *Petroleum Science and Technology* (Vol. 33, Issue 4, p. 397). Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10916466.2014.984075>
- Allahi , F., Taheri, S., Kian, R., & Sabet, E. (2020). Cash-Based Interventions to Enhance Dignity in Persistent Humanitarian Refugee Crises: A System Dynamics Approach. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* (Vol. 69, Issue 6, p. 3436). Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tem.2020.2982583>
- Altun, AE (2021). The Syrian Refugee Crisis in Turkey: Is Migration from Syria Bad for Turkey's Demographic and Economic Structure? Research Square. Research Square (United States). <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1110993/v1>
- Awaad, A. F. (2020). Iran-Saudi Rivalry over Regional Role... Syria as a Model. *Economics and Political Science Review*. Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/reps-07-2019-0094>
- Bahçekapili , C., & Çetin, B. (2015). The Impacts of Forced Migration on Regional Economies: The Case of Syrian Refugees in Turkey. *International Business Research* (Vol. 8, No. 9). Canadian Centre for Science and Education. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v8n9p1>
- Bichler, S. and Nitzan, J. (2014). Still About Oil. *EconStor Open Access Articles* (p. 49). http://bnarchives.yorku.ca/420/03/20141100_bn_still_about_oil_wpcasp.pdf
- Bichler, S. and Nitzan, J. (2014). The Weapondollar-Petrodollar Coalition: Still Interested in Oil? (Reprint). <http://bnarchives.yorku.ca/424/>

- Blondeel , M., Bradshaw , M., Bridge , G., & Kuzemko , C. (2021). Geopolitics of energy system transformation: A review [Geopolitics of energy system transformation: A review]. *Geography Compass*, 15(7). Wiley . <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12580>
- Blondeel, M., Bradshaw, M., Bridge, G., & Kuzemko, C. (2021). Geopolitics of energy system transformation: A review [Geopolitics of energy system transformation: A review]. *Geography Compass*, 15(7). Wiley . <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12580>
- Byman, D. (2018). *Understanding the Islamic State's Use of Terrorism* . Center for Strategic and International Studies.
- Dobbins, J., Martini, J., & Gordon, P. H. (2015). A Peace Plan for Syria. On RAND Corporation eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.7249/pe182>
- Fanon, F. (1961). *The Wretched of the Earth* . Grove Press.
- Fukuyama, F. (2004). *State Building: Governance and World Order in the 21st Century* . Cornell University Press.
- Gaber, S. (2020). Political discourse of President Bashar al-Assad after the Syrian revolution (analytical vision). In *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences* (Vol. 3, Issue 4, p. 239). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jhass-01-2020-0010>
- Hamam, HHM (2023). The Impact of the Internationalization of the Libyan Crisis on the Future of Political Solution. *مجلة Arabie السياسية* (Issue 65, p. 251). <https://doi.org/10.30907/jcopolicy.vi65.522>
- Holland, J. (2020). The Syrian Civil War. Cambridge University Press eBooks (p. 17). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108774314.002>
- Holland, J. (2020). The Syrian Civil War. Cambridge University Press eBooks (p. 17). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108774314.002>

- Hu, G., Yang, J., & Li, J. (2022). Dynamic Evolution of Global Energy Security and Geopolitical Games: 1995~2019. In International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (Vol. 19, Issue 21, p. 14584). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192114584>
- Jervis, R. (1978). *Cooperation Under the Security Dilemma* . World Politics, 30(2), 167-214.
- Kataibeh , OA, & AL-Labady, F. (2014). Guarantees the Protection of the Rights of Syrian Refugees in Jordan. In Politics and Law Journal (Vol. 7, No. 4). Canadian Centre for Science and Education. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jpl.v7n4p10>
- Liang, X. (2021). Humanitarian Environments for Syrian Refugees: Understanding the History of the Syrian Civil War. Advances in Social Sciences, Education, and Humanities Research/Advances in social sciences, education, and humanities research. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211020.151>
- Liang, X. (2021). Humanitarian Environments for Syrian Refugees: Understanding the History of the Syrian Civil War. Advances in Social Sciences, Education, and Humanities Research/Advances in social sciences, education, and humanities research. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211020.151>
- Liang, X. (2021). Humanitarian Environments for Syrian Refugees: Understanding the History of the Syrian Civil War. Advances in Social Sciences, Education, and Humanities Research/Advances in social sciences, education, and humanities research. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211020.151>
- Lynch, M. (2017). The Political and Institutional Impact of Syria's Displacement Crisis: An Introduction. Middle East Law and Governance (Vol. 9, No. 3, p. 223). Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18763375-00903003>
- Mearsheimer, J. J. (2001). *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics* . W. W. Norton & Company.
- Mumford, A. (2013). *Proxy War* . Politics

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Paris, R. (2004). *At War's End: Building Peace after the Civil War* . Cambridge University Press.
- Richmond, O. P. (1999). The Cyprus conflict, the changing norms of the international community and regional disjunctures. In *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* (Vol. 13, No. 1, p. 239). Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557579908400288>
- Said, E. (1978). *Orientalism* . Pantheon Books.
- Silverburg , S. R. and Alshdaifat , S. (2017). Syrians Displaced by the Civil War: What Does International Law Say? SSRN eJournal. RELX Group (The Netherlands). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3037854>
- Walther, O., & Pedersen, P. S. (2020). Rebel fragmentation in the Syrian civil war. *Small wars and insurgencies* (Vol. 31, Issue 3, p. 445). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2020.1726566>
- Waltz, K. N. (1979). *The Theory of International Politics* . Addison-Wesley.
- Wendt, A. (1992). *Anarchy is What States Mean by Anarchy: The Social Construction of Power Politics* . *International Organization*, ¹ 46(2), 391-425.
- Yergin, D. (2011). *The Quest: Energy, Security, and the Restructuring of the Modern World* . PenguinPress .